

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN PM 2.5 LEVEL AND RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTIONS AMONG CHILDREN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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S1. Completed STROBE Checklist for a Cross-Sectional Study on PM_{2.5} and Respiratory Tract Infections in Children

	Item No	Recommendation	Reported on page #
Title and abstract	1	(a) Indicate the study's design with a commonly used term in the title or the abstract	1
		(b) Provide in the abstract an informative and balanced summary of what was done and what was found	1
Introduction			
Background and rationale:	2	Explain the scientific background and rationale for the investigation being reported	2-3
Objectives:	3	State specific objectives, including any prespecified hypotheses	2-3
Methods			
Study design:	4	Present key elements of study design early in the paper	3-4
Setting:	5	Describe the setting, locations, and relevant dates, including periods of recruitment, data collection, and follow-up	4-8
Participants:	6	(a) Give the eligibility criteria, and the sources and methods of selection of participants	4-8
		(b) For matched studies, give matching criteria and number of exposed and unexposed	N/A
Variables:	7	Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors, potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable	6-11
Data sources/measurement:	8*	For each variable of interest, give sources of data and details of methods of assessment (measurement). Describe comparability of assessment methods if there is more than one group.	7-11
Bias:	9	Describe any efforts to address potential sources of bias	9-10
Study size:	10	Explain how the study size was arrived at	6-7
Quantitative variables:	11	Explain how quantitative variables were handled in the analyses. If applicable, describe which groupings were chosen and why	9-10
Statistical methods:	12	(a) Describe all statistical methods, including those used to control for confounding	9-10
		(b) Describe any methods used to examine subgroups and interactions	9-10
		(c) Explain how missing data were addressed	8
		(d) If applicable, explain how loss to follow-up was addressed for each outcome	8
		(e) Describe any sensitivity analyses	10
Results			
Participants:	13*	(a) Report numbers of individuals at each stage of study—e.g., numbers potentially eligible, examined for eligibility, confirmed eligible, included in the study, completing follow-up, and analysed	4-5
		(b) Give reasons for non-participation at each stage	5, 11
		(c) Consider use of a flow diagram	N/A
Descriptive data:	14*	(a) Give characteristics of study participants (e.g., demographic, clinical, social) and information on exposures and potential confounders	11-12
		(b) Indicate number of participants with missing data for each variable of interest	
Outcome data	15*	Report numbers of outcome events or summary measures	11-13
Main results	16	(a) Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-adjusted estimates and their precision (eg, 95% confidence interval). Make clear which confounders were adjusted for and why they were included	12-13
		(b) Report category boundaries when continuous variables were categorized	11-12
		(c) If relevant, consider translating estimates of relative risk into absolute risk for a meaningful time period	N/A
Other analyses	17	Report other analyses done—eg analyses of subgroups and interactions, and sensitivity analyses	9, 13-15
Discussion			
Key results	18	Summarise key results with reference to study objectives	16-18
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations of the study, taking into account sources of potential bias or imprecision. Discuss both direction and magnitude of any potential bias	19
Interpretation	20	Give a cautious overall interpretation of results considering objectives, limitations, multiplicity of analyses, results from similar studies, and other relevant evidence	16-21
Generalisability	21	Discuss the generalisability (external validity) of the study results	19-20
Other information			
Funding	22	Give the source of funding and the role of the funders for the present study and, if applicable, for the original study on which the present article is based	N/A

*Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups.

Note: This file is an author-completed version of the official STROBE Checklist for cross-sectional studies. The STROBE Initiative retains the original copyright.

S2. Statistical Analysis Results

- **S2.1: Chi-Square Test of Independence Results for Age Group Distribution between PM2.5 Exposure Groups.**

➔ Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
age * PM2.5	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

age * PM2.5 Crosstabulation

			PM2.5		Total
			low	high	
age	6-9 tahun	Count	22	20	42
		% within age	52.4%	47.6%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	37.9%	40.8%	39.3%
10-12 tahun	Count	36	29	65	
	% within age	55.4%	44.6%	100.0%	
	% within PM2.5	62.1%	59.2%	60.7%	
Total		Count	58	49	107
		% within age	54.2%	45.8%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.093 ^a	1	.761		
Continuity Correction ^b	.011	1	.916		
Likelihood Ratio	.093	1	.761		
Fisher's Exact Test				.843	.457
Linear-by-Linear Association	.092	1	.762		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 19.23.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

- **S2.2: Chi-Square Test of Independence Results for Gender Group Distribution between PM2.5 Exposure Groups.**

➔ Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
gender * PM2.5	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

gender * PM2.5 Crosstabulation

			PM2.5		Total
			low	high	
gender	male	Count	26	28	54
		% within gender	48.1%	51.9%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	44.8%	57.1%	50.5%
female	Count	32	21	53	
	% within gender	60.4%	39.6%	100.0%	
	% within PM2.5	55.2%	42.9%	49.5%	
Total		Count	58	49	107
		% within gender	54.2%	45.8%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.611 ^a	1	.204		
Continuity Correction ^b	1.156	1	.282		
Likelihood Ratio	1.616	1	.204		
Fisher's Exact Test				.246	.141
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.596	1	.206		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 24.27.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

○ **S2.3: Chi-Square Test of Independence between PM2.5 Exposure and Respiratory Tract Infections (RTI)**

➔ **Crosstabs**

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
PM2.5 * RTI	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

PM2.5 * RTI Crosstabulation

		RTI		Total
		no	yes	
PM2.5 low	Count	43	15	58
	% within PM2.5	74.1%	25.9%	100.0%
	% within RTI	75.4%	30.0%	54.2%
PM2.5 high	Count	14	35	49
	% within PM2.5	28.6%	71.4%	100.0%
	% within RTI	24.6%	70.0%	45.8%
Total	Count	57	50	107
	% within PM2.5	53.3%	46.7%	100.0%
	% within RTI	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.154 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	20.361	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	22.938	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	21.947	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 22.90.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

○ **S2.4: Chi-Square Test of Independence between Gender and Respiratory Tract Infections (RTI)**

➔ **Crosstabs**

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
gender * RTI	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

gender * RTI Crosstabulation

		RTI		Total
		no	yes	
gender male	Count	29	25	54
	% within gender	53.7%	46.3%	100.0%
	% within RTI	50.9%	50.0%	50.5%
gender female	Count	28	25	53
	% within gender	52.8%	47.2%	100.0%
	% within RTI	49.1%	50.0%	49.5%
Total	Count	57	50	107
	% within gender	53.3%	46.7%	100.0%
	% within RTI	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.008 ^a	1	.928		
Continuity Correction ^b	.000	1	1.000		
Likelihood Ratio	.008	1	.928		
Fisher's Exact Test				1.000	.541
Linear-by-Linear Association	.008	1	.928		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 24.77.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

○ **S2.5: Chi-Square Test of Association between Age (Categorized) and Respiratory Tract Infections (RTI)**

Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
age * RTI	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

age * RTI Crosstabulation

		RTI		Total	
		no	yes		
age	6.00	Count	0	1	1
		% within age	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within RTI	0.0%	2.0%	0.9%
7.00	Count	6	2	8	
	% within age	75.0%	25.0%	100.0%	
	% within RTI	10.5%	4.0%	7.5%	
8.00	Count	5	9	14	
	% within age	35.7%	64.3%	100.0%	
	% within RTI	8.8%	18.0%	13.1%	
9.00	Count	11	8	19	
	% within age	57.9%	42.1%	100.0%	
	% within RTI	19.3%	16.0%	17.8%	
10.00	Count	11	7	18	
	% within age	61.1%	38.9%	100.0%	
	% within RTI	19.3%	14.0%	16.8%	
11.00	Count	10	8	18	
	% within age	55.6%	44.4%	100.0%	
	% within RTI	17.5%	16.0%	16.8%	
12.00	Count	14	15	29	
	% within age	48.3%	51.7%	100.0%	
	% within RTI	24.6%	30.0%	27.1%	
Total	Count	57	50	107	
	% within age	53.3%	46.7%	100.0%	
	% within RTI	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.327 ^a	6	.503
Likelihood Ratio	5.809	6	.445
Linear-by-Linear Association	.031	1	.859
N of Valid Cases	107		

a. 4 cells (28.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .47.

- **S2.6: Detailed SPSS Output for Chi-Square Test of Association between PM2.5 Exposure and RTI in the Male Subgroup (n=54)**

Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
PM2.5 * RTI	54	100.0%	0	0.0%	54	100.0%

PM2.5 * RTI Crosstabulation

		RTI		Total
		no	yes	
PM2.5 low	Count	20	6	26
	% within PM2.5	76.9%	23.1%	100.0%
	% within RTI	69.0%	24.0%	48.1%
PM2.5 high	Count	9	19	28
	% within PM2.5	32.1%	67.9%	100.0%
	% within RTI	31.0%	76.0%	51.9%
Total	Count	29	25	54
	% within PM2.5	53.7%	46.3%	100.0%
	% within RTI	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.873 ^a	1	.001		
Continuity Correction ^b	9.147	1	.002		
Likelihood Ratio	11.308	1	.001		
Fisher's Exact Test				.001	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	10.672	1	.001		
N of Valid Cases	54				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 12.04.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

- **S2.7: Detailed SPSS Output for Chi-Square Test of Association between PM2.5 Exposure and RTI in the Female Subgroup (n=54)**

→ Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
PM2.5 * RTI	53	100.0%	0	0.0%	53	100.0%

PM2.5 * RTI Crosstabulation

		RTI		Total
		no	yes	
PM2.5 low	Count	23	9	32
	% within PM2.5	71.9%	28.1%	100.0%
	% within RTI	82.1%	36.0%	60.4%
PM2.5 high	Count	5	16	21
	% within PM2.5	23.8%	76.2%	100.0%
	% within RTI	17.9%	64.0%	39.6%
Total	Count	28	25	53
	% within PM2.5	52.8%	47.2%	100.0%
	% within RTI	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.755 ^a	1	.001		
Continuity Correction ^b	9.905	1	.002		
Likelihood Ratio	12.227	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.001	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.533	1	.001		
N of Valid Cases	53				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.91.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

○ **S2.8: Detailed SPSS Output for Chi-Square Test of Association between mother's education and PM2.5**

➔ Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
mother_education * PM2.5	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

mother_education * PM2.5 Crosstabulation

			PM2.5		Total
			low	high	
mother_education	low	Count	39	32	71
		% within mother_education	54.9%	45.1%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	67.2%	65.3%	66.4%
medium	medium	Count	19	17	36
		% within mother_education	52.8%	47.2%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	32.8%	34.7%	33.6%
Total	Total	Count	58	49	107
		% within mother_education	54.2%	45.8%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.045 ^a	1	.833		
Continuity Correction ^b	.000	1	.995		
Likelihood Ratio	.045	1	.833		
Fisher's Exact Test				.840	.497
Linear-by-Linear Association	.044	1	.834		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 16.49.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

○ **S2.9: Detailed SPSS Output for Chi-Square Test of Association between mother's occupation and PM2.5**

➔ Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
mother_occupation * PM2.5	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

mother_occupation * PM2.5 Crosstabulation

			PM2.5		Total
			low	high	
mother_occupation	blue collar	Count	47	40	87
		% within mother_occupation	54.0%	46.0%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	81.0%	81.6%	81.3%
semi-professional	semi-professional	Count	11	9	20
		% within mother_occupation	55.0%	45.0%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	19.0%	18.4%	18.7%
Total	Total	Count	58	49	107
		% within mother_occupation	54.2%	45.8%	100.0%
		% within PM2.5	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.006 ^a	1	.937		
Continuity Correction ^b	.000	1	1.000		
Likelihood Ratio	.006	1	.937		
Fisher's Exact Test				1.000	.569
Linear-by-Linear Association	.006	1	.937		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.16.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

- **S2.10: Detailed SPSS Output for Chi-Square Test of Association between mother's education and RTI**

➔ **Crosstabs**

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
mother_education * RTI	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

mother_education * RTI Crosstabulation

			RTI		Total
			no	yes	
mother_education	low	Count	39	32	71
		% within mother_education	54.9%	45.1%	100.0%
		% within RTI	68.4%	64.0%	66.4%
medium	medium	Count	18	18	36
		% within mother_education	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
		% within RTI	31.6%	36.0%	33.6%
Total	Total	Count	57	50	107
		% within mother_education	53.3%	46.7%	100.0%
		% within RTI	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.233 ^a	1	.629		
Continuity Correction ^b	.077	1	.781		
Likelihood Ratio	.233	1	.629		
Fisher's Exact Test				.684	.390
Linear-by-Linear Association	.231	1	.631		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 16.82.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

- **S2.11: Detailed SPSS Output for Chi-Square Test of Association between mother's occupation and RTI**

➔ **Crosstabs**

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
mother_occupation * RTI	107	100.0%	0	0.0%	107	100.0%

mother_occupation * RTI Crosstabulation

			RTI		Total
			no	yes	
mother_occupation	blue collar	Count	45	42	87
		% within mother_occupation	51.7%	48.3%	100.0%
		% within RTI	78.9%	84.0%	81.3%
semi-professional	semi-professional	Count	12	8	20
		% within mother_occupation	60.0%	40.0%	100.0%
		% within RTI	21.1%	16.0%	18.7%
Total	Total	Count	57	50	107
		% within mother_occupation	53.3%	46.7%	100.0%
		% within RTI	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	447 ^a	1	.504		
Continuity Correction ^b	.177	1	.674		
Likelihood Ratio	451	1	.502		
Fisher's Exact Test				.621	.399
Linear-by-Linear Association	443	1	.506		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.35.
 b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

- **S2.12: Detailed SPSS Output for Crosstabulation of PM2.5 Exposure and Respiratory Tract Infections with Phi and Cramer's V**

		Symmetric Measures			Monte Carlo Significance	
		Value	Approximate Significance	Significance	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.475	.000	.000 ^a	.000	.000
	Cramer's V	.475	.000	.000 ^a	.000	.000
N of Valid Cases		107				

c. Based on 10000 sampled tables with starting seed 2000000.

- **S2.13: Comparison of Odds Ratio Estimates for Respiratory Tract Infection (RTI) and PM2.5 Exposure from Logistic Regression, Risk Estimate, and Mantel-Haenszel Analysis**

➔ **Logistic Regression**

Case Processing Summary

Unweighted Cases ^a		N	Percent
Selected Cases	Included in Analysis	107	100.0
	Missing Cases	0	.0
	Total	107	100.0
Unselected Cases		0	.0
Total		107	100.0

a. If weight is in effect, see classification table for the total number of cases.

Dependent Variable Encoding

Original Value	Internal Value
no	0
yes	1

Categorical Variables Codings

		Frequency	Parameter coding (1)
PM2.5	low	58	-.500
	high	49	.500

Block 0: Beginning Block

Classification Table^{a,b}

		Predicted			
		RTI		Percentage Correct	
Observed		no	yes		
Step 0	RTI	no	57	0	100.0
		yes	50	0	.0
Overall Percentage					53.3

a. Constant is included in the model.

b. The cut value is .500

Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 0 Constant	-.131	.194	.457	1	.499	.877

Variables not in the Equation

	Score	df	Sig.
Step 0 Variables	PM2.5(1)	22.154	1 .000
Overall Statistics		22.154	1 .000

Block 1: Method = Enter

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1 Step	22.938	1	.000
Block	22.938	1	.000
Model	22.938	1	.000

Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	124.937 ^a	.193	.258

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 4 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	.000	0	.

Contingency Table for Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

		RTI = no		RTI = yes		Total
		Observed	Expected	Observed	Expected	
Step 1	1	43	43.000	15	15.000	58
	2	14	14.000	35	35.000	49

Classification Table^a

		Predicted		Percentage Correct
		no	yes	
Step 1	RTI = no	43	14	75.4
	yes	15	35	70.0
Overall Percentage				72.9

a. The cut value is .500

Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for Exp(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Step 1 ^a PM2.5(1)	1.989	.436	20.423	1	.000	7.167	3.050	16.837
Constant	-.068	.218	.099	1	.753	.934		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: PM2.5.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.154 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	20.361	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	22.938	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	21.947	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	107				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 22.90.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.455			.000
	Cramer's V	.455			.000
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.455	.086	5.236	.000 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.455	.086	5.236	.000 ^c
N of Valid Cases		107			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
c. Based on normal approximation.

Risk Estimate

	Value	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower	Upper
Odds Ratio for PM2.5 (low / high)	7.167	3.050	16.837
For cohort RTI = no	2.595	1.625	4.144
For cohort RTI = yes	.362	.226	.580
N of Valid Cases	107		

PM2.5 * RTI Crosstabulation

Count		RTI		Total
		no	yes	
PM2.5	low	43	15	58
	high	14	35	49
Total		57	50	107

Tests of Homogeneity of the Odds Ratio

	Chi-Squared	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Breslow-Day	.000	0	.
Tarone's	.000	0	.

Tests of Conditional Independence

	Chi-Squared	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Cochran's	22.154	1	.000
Mantel-Haenszel	20.171	1	.000

Under the conditional independence assumption, Cochran's statistic is asymptotically distributed as a 1 df chi-squared distribution, only if the number of strata is fixed, while the Mantel-Haenszel statistic is always asymptotically distributed as a 1 df chi-squared distribution. Note that the continuity correction is removed from the Mantel-Haenszel statistic when the sum of the differences between the observed and the expected is 0.

Mantel-Haenszel Common Odds Ratio Estimate

Estimate	7.167		
ln(Estimate)	1.969		
Standard Error of ln(Estimate)	.436		
Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	.000		
Asymptotic 95% Confidence Interval	Common Odds Ratio	Lower Bound	3.050
		Upper Bound	16.837
	ln(Common Odds Ratio)	Lower Bound	1.115
		Upper Bound	2.824

The Mantel-Haenszel common odds ratio estimate is asymptotically normally distributed under the common odds ratio of 1.000 assumption. So is the natural log of the estimate.

- **S2.14: Multivariate Binary Logistic Regression Analysis for Confounding Factors Associated with Respiratory Tract Infections (RTIs) among Children, Hosmer-Lemeshow test.**

Logistic Regression

Case Processing Summary

Unweighted Cases ^a		N	Percent
Selected Cases	Included in Analysis	107	100.0
	Missing Cases	0	.0
	Total	107	100.0
Unselected Cases		0	.0
Total		107	100.0

a. If weight is in effect, see classification table for the total number of cases.

Dependent Variable Encoding

Original Value	Internal Value
no	0
yes	1

Categorical Variables Codings

		Frequency	Parameter coding (1)
mother_occupation	blue collar	87	-.500
	semi-professional	20	.500
gender	male	54	1.000
	female	53	.000
mother_education	low	71	1.000
	medium	36	.000
PM2.5	low	58	-.500
	high	49	.500

Block 0: Beginning Block

Classification Table^{a,b}

Observed	RTI	Predicted		Percentage Correct
		no	yes	
Step 0	no	57	0	100.0
	yes	50	0	.0
Overall Percentage				53.3

- a. Constant is included in the model.
b. The cut value is .500

Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	
Step 0	Constant	-.131	.194	.457	1	.499	.877

Variables not in the Equation

Step 0	Variables	Score	df	Sig.
	PM2.5(1)	22.154	1	.000
	gender(1)	.008	1	.928
	age	.022	1	.882
	mother_education(1)	.233	1	.629
	mother_occupation(1)	.447	1	.504
Overall Statistics		24.439	5	.000

Block 1: Method = Enter

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

Step 1	Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
	Step	25.854	5	.000
	Block	25.854	5	.000
	Model	25.854	5	.000

Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	122.022 ^a	.215	.287

- a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 4 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	4.643	8	.795

Contingency Table for Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step 1	RTI = no	RTI = yes		Total	
		Observed	Expected		
1	7	5.736	0	1.264	7
2	11	11.916	4	3.084	15
3	5	6.294	3	1.706	8
4	9	7.913	2	3.087	11
5	8	7.724	3	3.276	11
6	5	4.665	4	4.335	9
7	3	3.664	8	7.336	11
8	4	3.923	8	8.077	12
9	3	3.867	12	11.133	15
10	2	1.299	6	6.701	8

Classification Table^a

Observed	RTI	Predicted		Percentage Correct
		no	yes	
Step 1	no	43	14	75.4
	yes	15	35	70.0
Overall Percentage				72.9

- a. The cut value is .500

Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
Step 1 ^a	PM2.5(1)	2.065	.455	20.547	1	.000	7.883	3.228 19.250
	gender(1)	-.429	.464	.856	1	.355	.651	.262 1.616
	age	.019	.455	.002	1	.969	1.019	.418 2.483
	mother_education(1)	-.786	.842	1.590	1	.211	.456	.130 1.602
	mother_occupation(1)	-1.159	.790	2.150	1	.143	.314	.067 1.477
	Constant	.279	.852	.187	1	1.443	1.322	

- a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: PM2.5, gender, age, mother_education, mother_occupation.

		RTI = no		RTI = yes		Total
		Observed	Expected	Observed	Expected	
Step 1	1	7	5.736	0	1.264	7
	2	11	11.916	4	3.084	15
	3	5	6.294	3	1.706	8
	4	9	7.913	2	3.087	11
	5	8	7.724	3	3.276	11
	6	5	4.665	4	4.335	9
	7	3	3.664	8	7.336	11
	8	4	3.923	8	8.077	12
	9	3	3.867	12	11.133	15
	10	2	1.299	6	6.701	8

Observed	Predicted	RTI		Percentage Correct
		no	yes	
Step 1 RTI no	no	43	14	75.4
	yes	15	35	70.0
Overall Percentage				72.9

a. The cut value is .500

Step 1 ^a	PM2.5(t)	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
								Lower	Upper
	gender(t)	-.429	.464	.856	1	.355	.651	.262	1.616
	age	.019	.455	.002	1	.968	1.019	.418	2.483
	mother_education(t)	-.786	.642	1.500	1	.221	.456	.130	1.602
	mother_occupation(t)	-1.159	.790	2.150	1	.143	.314	.067	1.477
	Constant	.279	.852	.107	1	.743	1.322		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: PM2.5, gender, age, mother_education, mother_occupation.

S2.15: Standardized residuals versus predicted probabilities from Multivariate Binary Logistic Regression Analysis

GRAPH

```
/SCATTERPLOT(BIVAR)=PRE_3 WITH ZRE_3
/MISSING=LISTWISE.
```

Graph

